

FORMULATION AND SHELF LIFE EVALUATION OF QUINOA INCORPORATED INSTANT MIX (DOSA)

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ABSTRACT:

The instant dosa mix is designed for convenience, requiring minimal preparation time, making it ideal for health-conscious consumers and those with limited cooking resources. This study focuses on formulating an instant dosa mix by combining brown rice flour, quinoa flour, and wheatgrass powder in optimized proportions. The formulation also includes lentil flour to improve protein content, fiber content and functional properties. Quinoa, a pseudo-cereal, is an excellent source of high-quality protein, dietary fiber, and essential amino acids, making it suitable for enhancing the protein content of traditional foods. Wheatgrass powder, known for its richness in vitamins, iron, calcium, and antioxidants, provides significant nutritional benefits, particularly for individuals suffering from anaemia. Nutritional analysis of the mix reveals a significant improvement in protein, dietary fiber, and micronutrient content, especially iron and folate, which are critical in combating anaemia and protein addresses the malnutrition. The product's shelf-life is assessed to ensure stability under different storage conditions, focusing on moisture content. Sensory evaluation confirms the product's acceptability, with favourable scores for taste, texture, and overall appeal.

KEYWORDS:

QUINOA, WHEATGRASS POWDER, IRON, PROTEIN, FIBER, ANAEMIA, MALNUTRITION.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Convenience foods have gained popularity in India. Cake mixes, juice boxes, frozen peas, processed or frozen chapatis, and other readily consumable food items are seen to be flying off the shelves. These foods, which are typically categorized as ready-to-eat, ready-to-cook, ready-to-serve, or frozen foods, are growing in popularity as people spend less money (Mansur, 2018). Tertiary processed foods, often known as instant foods, are made to save consumers time in the kitchen, cut down on spoiling expenses, and use economies of scale. This category comprises dehydrated meals that only need water to be prepared. The idea of instant meal has been around for a while in the developed world, but it has only just entered the Indian market (Siddiqui, 2014). In India, most food is still consumed at home. However, the rise in urbanization, rising rural income, changing rural lifestyle, dissolution of the traditional joint family system, need for quality time, growing number of working women, elevated per capita income, and rising middle-class affluence have all contributed to the rise in out-of-home food consumption. Advanced technology has made "instant food" and

"readymade food" more convenient for the past 20 years globally, and working people are the ones who use it the most. The phrase "instant foods" refers to simple, quick, and easy meals that are not only hygienic and convenient to consume, but also easy and quick to prepare. (Shanmugapriya & Srivarshini, 2018). The majority of RTC customers are urban dwellers, especially bachelors and city dwellers with hectic schedules (Malik and Kajla, 2020). Because of their high vitamin and calorie content, simplicity in preparation, and short serving time, instant mixes can be used as a breakfast substitute (Gokulakrishnan, 2014). Approximately 15–25% of our daily energy consumption should be consumed at breakfast, which equates to 300–500 calories for women and 375–625 for men, according to the most recent research (Spencer, 2017).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Quinoa is a very nutrient-dense grain that contains a good amount of high-quality protein along with all the necessary vitamins, minerals, and amino acids (Vilche et al., 2003).

Quinoa may be utilized as a source of antioxidants in addition to being a strong supply of minerals and proteins (Bogdan Debski et al. 2013). Compared to maize and barley, quinoa has greater quantities of iron (81 mg/kg), calcium (874 mg/kg), and phosphorus (Ahmed et al., 1998b). Albumins and globulins make up the majority of the protein in pseudocereals like quinoa (44–77% of total protein), which is higher than that of (0.5–7.0%) prolamins (Matiacevich et al. 2006). Quinoa provides 0.20 mg of vitamin B6, 0.61 mg of pantothenic acid, 23.5 g of folic acid, and 7.1 g of biotin per 100 g edible portion (Bhargava, 2006). Wheatgrass, or *Triticum speices*, is the largest edible grain cereal-grass crop in the world. It belongs to the Gramineae (Poaceae) family. Wheatgrass is the term for the common wheat plant's juvenile grass (Mujoriya, 2011). It is a functional or consumable food that can be consumed as fresh juice, dried powder, or tablets (Sunil D Kulkarni et al., 2006; Rajagopalan and Shakya, 2014). The grass has been shown to be incredibly nutrient-dense due to its high levels of protein, necessary and non-essential amino acids, vitamin C, minerals, enzymes, and chlorophyll (Chauhan, 2014).

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Raw materials: Some of the raw materials required for development of instant dosa mix are Quinoa, Wheatgrass powder, Brown rice, Urad dal, Chana dal, Rice flakes, Salt, Baking soda, Citric acid.

The procurement of raw materials like quinoa and wheatgrass powder is from nearby local market of Anantapuramu and the remaining raw materials are from Industry.

PROCESS OF ROASTING

The ingredients are selected for roasting process. The ingredients like quinoa, urad dal chana dal and brown rice are graded sorted and cleaned by traditional method. The ingredients are placed in a nonstick pan and roasted one by one. Take the induction stove place the pan and add the ingredients one by one and roast it. Particular ingredient has particular temperature like Quinoa: 150 -170°C20-30mins, Brown rice: 175°C10-15mins Urad dal: medium flame for 15mins, Chana dal: 200°C 25-30mins.

PROCESS OF PULVERIZING

After roasting the ingredients, the ingredients are shifted to the pulverizer. The pulverizer is a mechanical device used to crush, grind, or pulverize solid materials into smaller particles or powders.

PROCESS OF VIBRO SHIFTER:

After pulverizing the processed material is shifted to vibro shifter. The material is fed onto the center of a vibrating screen. The machine vibrates and vibration causes the material to move across the screen. Fine particles pass through the mesh openings and coarser or oversized particles stay on top and move toward the discharge outlet. Fine powder is collected separately. Oversized material can either be reprocessed or discarded.

PREPARATION OF DOSA MIX POWDER

The product obtained is weighed accurately. The weighed product is added one by one into the blender. Accordingly all the products are added to the blender. Now the blender is used for mixing all the ingredients into the equal proportions. The blending process will be of 10 -15mins. After that the product obtained is ready for preparation.

PROCESS OF FILLING AND SEALING

The obtained finished goods is filled in a tetra -pouches or the Low Density Polyethylene pouches. The pouch consists of zip lock at the top of the pouch. The product is filled according to the pouch size. The product filled in the pouch is sealed in a continuous sealer machine. The sealed product is kept for storage stability.

FLOW CHART OF INSTANT DOSA MIX

FORMULATIONS

The formulation is made in the point of view that main ingredient like quinoa should have high percentage than other ingredients because the quinoa is packed with protein and wheatgrass powder is another ingredient where it provides iron to the mix. The brown rice which is rich in nutrients are added. The difference in formulation 3 and 4 is the mesh size. From formulation 1 to 4 the difference is that increasing the amount of quinoa and decreasing the brown rice urad dal. The total formulation is made up to 150g

TABLE: 1 FORMULATIONS

Quinoa	52	57	62	62
Wheatgrass powder	12	10	9	9
Brown rice	39	37	34	34
Urad dal	29	28	27	27
Channa dal	8	8	8	8
Rice flakes	7	7	7	7
Salt	2	2	2	2
Baking soda	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Citric acid	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

PREPARATION OF DOSA

The dosa mix powder is taken in a bowl after unsealing. Properly mix the dosa mix powder in the bowl.

Application 1: Take the dosa mix powder add sufficient water into it as per your consistency. Mix it properly without any lumps.

Application 2: Take the dosa mix powder add curd into it. Mix it properly and leave it for 15 to 30 mins.

Pour the batter on the pan, after the dosa turns brown take it in the plate and have it.

METHODS

Moisture content: To measure the accurate amount of water present in the sample. Moisture content is analyzed by the oven drying method at 105°C for 3hrs (AOAC 2000).

Formula: $Moisture = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100\%$

Ash content: To measure the minerals present in it. Ash content is analyzed by using muffle furnace at 550°C for 6hrs (AOAC 2000).

Formula: $Ash = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100\%$

pH: It is determined by the digital pH meter.

Titration acidity: The measure of un -disassociated acids in the sample.

Formula: $Acidity = \frac{Titrate\ value \times equivalent\ weight\ of\ NaOH \times normality\ of\ NaOH}{weight\ of\ the\ sample}$

Acid Insoluble Ash: To measure contaminants like sand in the sample (AOAC 941.12)

Formula: $Acid\ insoluble\ ash = \frac{weight\ of\ residue\ after\ acid\ treatment}{Original\ weight\ of\ the\ sample} \times 100\%$

Carbohydrates: the measure of carbohydrates is by using fehling solution performed according to FSSAI manual method.

Formula: $Total\ Carbohydrates\ (\%) = \frac{Volume\ of\ sample\ used\ (ml) \times dilution\ factor \times 100}{}$

Protein: the protein content is determined by kjeldahl method.

Formula: $Nitrogen\% = \frac{(Volume\ of\ HCl \times Normality\ of\ HCl \times 1.4007)}{Weight\ of\ sample\ in\ gm}$
 Protein (%) = Nitrogen (%) × 6.38

Crude fiber: Determined using the method of AOAC (2000).

Formula: $Crude\ fibre = \frac{Weight\ of\ the\ fibre\ [(W_2 - W_1) - (W_3 - W_1)] \times 100}{Weight\ of\ the\ sample\ (g)}$

Phosphorous: Determined according to the Fiske and Row's method described by Ranganna (2011) by spectrophotometer.

Sensory Analysis: the sensory analysis is done according to hedonic scale rating (table 2). The formulations are exposed to sensory analysis along with control. Different panelist gave the rating for sensory attributes like color, flavor, taste, appearance, taste and overall acceptability. The mean score is the overall acceptability.

TABLE: 2 HEDONIC SCALE

OPINION	RATING
Like extremely	9
Like very much	8
Like moderately	7
Like slightly	6
Neither like nor dislike	5
Dislike slightly	4
Dislike moderately	3
Dislike very much	2
Dislike extremely	1

4. RESULTS

Sensory Analysis: According to sensory analysis the formulation 4 that is 62g quinoa powder, 9 g wheatgrass powder, 34g brown rice powder, 27g urad dal powder, 7g chana dal powder, 8g rice flakes 2g salt, 0.5 g baking soda and 0.5 g citric acid is the best among the 3 as it has highest rating due it is better in taste, appearance and texture. The overall acceptability for the formulation 1 is 8.5, formulation 2 is 8.5 formulation 3 is 7 and formulation 4 is 9.

TABLE: 3 SENSORY ANALYSIS

Sensorial Attributes	F1	F2	F3	F4
Color	8	7.5	7	9
Consistency	8	8.5	7	8.5
Flavor	7.5	7.5	8	8.5
Taste	8	8	8	8.5
Appearance	8.5	8.5	8.5	9
Overall Acceptability	8.5	8.5	7	9

PHYSICO CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

According to the physico chemical analysis it clearly states that the developed and standardize product is less in the moisture, ash, and acid insoluble ash when compared to control. It was also expressed that the moisture content, ash content acid insoluble content is decreasing where it indicates that the shelf life stability is increased, retention in mineral is also less and the inorganic matter like sand dust and other foreign particles also less when compared to other formulations.

The formulation 4 has less moisture content 8.01%, ash 1.12%, acid insoluble ash 0.42%, pH 4.3%, acidity 0.6%. The other formulations and control has high in moisture content, ash content.

TABLE: 4 PHYSICO CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

PARAMETERS	Control	F1	F2	F3	F4
Moisture	11.08%	8.06%	8.01%	8.08%	8.01%
.Ash	3.2%	1.1%	1.2%	1%	1.12%
Acid insoluble ash	0.5%	0.45%	0.459%	0.43%	0.42%
pH	5.4	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.3
Acidity	0.81%	0.57%	0.53%	0.62%	0.6%

NUTRITIONAL ANALYSIS

The nutritional analysis of 4 formulations are given in the below table. According to the sensory evaluation the formulation 4 is the best as it has high protein, fiber, iron, phosphorous and folate when compared to control. The dosa is rich in nutrients which it can be healthy when it is consumed. The formulation 4 has less amount of carbohydrates 60.97g, high amount of protein 12.50g, high amount of fiber 7.33g, high amount of iron 4.28mg, amount of phosphorous 228mg and folate content is 90µg. The control sample has high amount of carbohydrates, less amount of protein fiber and iron and zero amount of phosphorous and folate.

The iron and folate content can treat for anaemia and protein content can treat for malnutrition.

TABLE: 5 NUTRITIONAL ANALYSIS

PARAMETERS	Control	F1	F2	F3	F4
Carbohydrates	65.64	61.45	60.23	60.05	60.97
Protein	10.14	11.24	11.90	11.98	12.50
Fiber	6.70	6.5	6.8	6.99	7.33
Iron	3.56	3.98	4.08	4.12	4.28
Phosphorous	-----	212	219	228	228
Folate	-----	80	84	92	90

MICROBIAL ANALYSIS:

The microbial analysis was done in 0 days and 30 days and 60 days. The microbial analysis is done for formulation 4.

According to FSSAI standards the microbial load is acceptable for ready to cook mixes at regular intervals of time (table 6). In the initial stage the colony formulation is nil and there is increase in the 60 days. The microbial load is within limit.

TABLE: 6 MICROBIAL ANALYSIS

0 Days	30days	60days
Nil	6.9*10 ³ CFU/ml	7.6*10 ³ CFU/ml

STORAGE STUDY OF THE INSTANT DOSA MIX FORMULATION

Tests were conducted to determine the shelf life of functional foods. The packaging materials—a low density polyethylene pouch (LDPE), ziplock pouches and aluminated pouches used to store the developed instant dosa mix meal. These pouches are stored and recorded the how much percent of moisture content is absorbed by the packet and also visualized the product whether the sample is affected with rice weevil and any colour disappearance. The product is visualized after some days and the product is not affected by any insects. The product's stability and quality are not impacted by the storage temperature. The product is studied at room temperature (28°C) on their stability was investigated.

5. CONCLUSION

By the above results it may conclude that the dosa mix is high in protein and slight less in carbohydrates hence it is acceptable. The instant dosa mix with quinoa and wheatgrass is an innovative product that meets the modern consumer's needs for health, convenience, and taste. A convenience food product saves the cooking time and easy to prepare that is just adding curd or water. The microbial analysis reveals that the product can be stored for 60 days. It successfully combines traditional culinary appeal with enhanced nutritional value, creating a balanced, functional meal solution.

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